

**ADMINISTRATIVE TERMS OF HIGHER EDUCATION IN THE
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Annotation: New concepts mean new words or new terms. Indeed, terms borrowed from other languages have their place in the Karakalpak language. They contribute to the enrichment of the Karakalpak language to a certain extent. The role of foreign terms in accurately defining various concepts is crucial both in everyday life and in the field of education. The article divides foreign higher education terms thematically into groups. Specifically, administrative higher education terms are explained separately. Among higher education terms, administrative terms are of great importance.

Keywords: term, words, compound term, administrative terms, higher education

The enrichment of the Karakalpak language's vocabulary, including its terminological vocabulary, is not a spontaneous phenomenon. As a result of internal and external influences, the Karakalpak language was significantly enriched. This process continues to this day. However, it is impossible to assimilate all foreign words into the Karakalpak language.

Looking back at history, the frequent borrowing of words and terms from Arabic, Persian, and Russian is linked to the political, cultural, and economic conditions of the population at that time. We can learn this from the works of poets and writers of those times. For example, the frequent use of Arabic and Persian terms in the works of Ajiniyaz proves our point. Today, along with Russian, we frequently encounter the use of English, Latin, and Greek terms in the Karakalpak language. This, in turn, is connected with political and economic life. At this point, among the terms of higher education received from abroad, it is appropriate to note the following terms: applicant, author, abstract, academic, analysis, postgraduate student, postgraduate studies, assessment, assistant, auditorium, bachelor, bachelor's degree, score, bibliography, binary lecture, variant, statement, video lesson (video view), virtual education, grant, group, dean, dean's office, dictation, diploma, director, discussion, dissertation, report, doctoral studies, doctoral student, doctoral, associate professor, entrance exam, induction, innovation, institute, office, department, candidate, case study, cluster, cognitive, congress, conference, competition, conservatory, summary, contract,

corruption, coaching, credit, curator, course, laboratory assistant, laboratory assistant, lecturer, lecture, master's student, master's student, material, method, methodology, minimum, monograph, online, opponent, offline, teacher, pedagogy, pedagogical institute, plagiarism (antiplagiarism), plan, practice, vice-rector, professor, PhD, registration office, rector, rector's office, resource, rating, abstract, semester, seminar, session, symposium, synthesis, slide, council, article, scholarship, scholarship holder, student, science (DSc - sciense), scopus, thesis, transcript, university, faculty, branch Such imported terms are often encountered in higher education institutions.

When analyzing higher education terms, it is advisable to study them by dividing them into groups (terms related to academic affairs, scientific terms, management terms).

In our article, we will discuss higher education terms related to the management process:

Assistant - (lat. assistent - participating, assisting) 1. Specialist's assistant. Assistant Professor 2. The position of junior lecturer in higher education institutions and the holder of this position. (QQTs. Volume I, p. 201) M. Temirbayeva, assistant teacher of the Department of Journalism, visited the "Yoshlar TV" TV channel with the 5th-year correspondence students of the specialty "Journalism" assigned to her (from the Karsu.uz website).

Dean - noun. (lat. decanus - head). A person who heads a faculty in higher educational institutions. A professor or specialist is trained by order of the university rector. The Dean manages academic, educational, and scientific affairs at the faculty and serves as the head of the faculty's academic council. (QQTs. Volume III, page 133 The Dean of the Faculty of Mathematics, J.X.Seypullaev, was awarded in the "Most Active Faculty Dean of the Year" nomination (from Karsu.uz website).

Vice-Rector. One of the high positions in higher education institutions. (Volume VI, page 95) The event was chaired by S. Alawatdinov, First Vice-Rector for Youth Affairs and Spiritual and Educational Work (from the Karsu.uz website).

The registrar's office is the main department in higher education institutions that manages students' academic records (grades, subjects), manages the educational process (class schedules, exams), and processes documents (from thetsuull.uz website). it serves students and teachers, providing them with academic education.

Rector - noun. Head of the university (Volume VI, page 133). The rector of KSU inspected the activities of educational and scientific laboratories at the Faculties of Construction and Economics (from the website Karsu.uz).

The transcript is prepared and issued to the student upon their departure for study abroad or upon transfer. The transcript is issued mainly to students studying in the credit grading system (from the website hemis.uz). Students wishing to transfer and resume their studies must enter their personal identification information into the electronic platform and upload the following documents: an academic certificate or transcript copy (from the NDPI.uz website).

Tutor (Latin - teacher, instructor, trainer). An employee who works with students at higher education institutions, guiding them in the educational process, acting as a consultant and mentor. As group trainers, they help students master their lessons and spend their free time meaningfully (from the yuz.uz website). Presentations are being held on the results of tutors' work in the field of education and upbringing and their future tasks (from the NMPI.uz website).

Faculty name A section, field, sector, or branch of science taught by a specific specialist in higher and specialized educational institutions (Volume VII). Page 321) Students of the Karakalpak Language and Literature Faculty of the institute also participated in the scientific conference (K. Ayimbetov).

Hemis (HEMIS - Higher Education Management Information System) is a unified electronic information system designed to manage the educational process of higher education institutions in Uzbekistan (from the uz.wikipedia website). Also, in today's era of globalization, the negative impact of various alien ideas on the upbringing of young people and the tasks aimed at its prevention, as well as the educational program and credit-modular system, were widely explained to parents (from the Karsu.uz website).

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